

Prosiding Seminar Nasional
Adiwidya 9
Pascasarjana ITB

**“SMART CITY AS AN ALTERNATIVE SOLUTION
FOR URBAN DEVELOPMENT AND EQUITY IN
INDONESIA”**

Dilakukan secara daring, 23-24 Oktober 2021

PROSIDING ADIWIDYA 9

SMART CITY AS AN ALTERNATIVE SOLUTION FOR URBAN DEVELOPMENT AND EQUITY IN INDONESIA

- ◆ *Talkshow Smart Education*
- ◆ *Talkshow Smart Social Economy*
- ◆ *Talkshow Smart Science Technology*
- ◆ *International Webinar Smart City*

ADIWIDYA 9 | #SINERGIKANPERAN
KAMIL PASCASARJANA ITB

Determination of Scholarship Amount with Mamdani's Fuzzy Inference System (FIS)

Aulia Nuril Isnia

Department of Mathematics, Faculty of Mathematics and Natural Science, State University of Malang

Corresponding author: aulianurilisnia@gmail.com

Abstract. Regency Education Office is one of the government agencies that play a role in education. Under the coordination of the Regional Government, there is a policy regarding a grant in aid to local underprivileged undergraduate students through scholarships. The determination of its amount has been done manually by considering the location of the university and the tuition fee for each applicant's study program. The process carried out does not include clear rules and boundaries. Fuzzy Inference System (FIS) functions to control any process by using inference rules based on fuzzy logic. This paper aims to describe the steps and determine the results of the determination of the scholarship amount using the Fuzzy Mamdani defuzzification Centroid method. The system is built based on distance data, regency minimum wage, and tuition fees from the prospective scholarship recipients' college location.

Keywords: Centroid method, FIS Mamdani, fuzzy logic, scholarship amount

1. Introductions

Education in Indonesia is not yet evenly distributed, even though it is one of the elements in the Human Development Index (HDI) [15]. One of the government's efforts to support the target of increasing Indonesia's HDI [11] is providing scholarships [7]. Despite the policy, some scholarships are mistargeted because the rules and boundaries are not clear [2]. On the other hand, there are human limitations in carrying out sensory tasks for a long time and large capacity due to subjectivity.

One alternative to determine the amount of the scholarship is through the implementation of mathematics with the help of computer tools. One of the branches of mathematics to solve scholarship amount determination problem is fuzzy logic. It is an appropriate way to map an input space into an output space [14]. The advantages of this are easy to understand, flexible, and have tolerance for inaccurate data. Fuzzy logic can be used as a decision-making system or commonly known as a fuzzy inference system (FIS).

The results of a research [9] regarding the prediction of the number of new student registrants concluded that the error rate of the Mamdani fuzzy method was 19.76%. This percentage is smaller than the error rate of the Tsukamoto methods (39.03%) and the Sugeno methods (86.41%). In addition, the Mamdani method is being a recommendation because the calculation results are close to the actual results [12]. The information input process resembles how the human brain works [1]. Mamdani method has several defuzzification methods. The Centroid method has ease of calculation. Its other advantage is that the defuzzification value moves smoothly so that changes from a fuzzy set

will also run smoothly [13]. Based on the explanation, it is necessary to determine the amount of scholarship using the FIS Mamdani.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Fuzzy Logic

Zadeh is the first fuzzy logic developer [10]. Fuzzy logic is a generalization of classical logic with tolerance for ambiguity [8]. There are several terms in fuzzy logic [14], such as variables, sets, a universe of speech, and domains. The popular representations of the membership function are linear up/down and triangular/trapezoidal/shoulder curves. The basic operators (AND, OR, NOT) are for combining and modifying fuzzy sets. The membership value as a result of two sets operation is known as fire strength or α -predicate.

2.2 FIS Mamdani

FIS is a widely developed method to control processes using inference rules. The system consists of four units: fuzzification, knowledge base, reasoning, and defuzzification. The final result came from calculating the z-weighted average with the following formula:

$$z = \frac{\alpha_1 z_1 + \alpha_2 z_2}{\alpha_1 + \alpha_2}$$

Mamdani method is popularly known as Min-Max. The output of the fuzzy rule is decided by the Min method. The results are then interfered with using the Max method. The operation process in the Mamdani method is more complex so that it can cover a wide field or is intuitive [1].

3. Methods

Based on the results of interviews obtained information about the problem of scholarships. The literature study is from reference sources such as fuzzy logic books, articles related to the FIS Mamdani, similar research, and tutorials on using a calculation tool.

After getting results, an analytical method is to adjust the results of determining the amount of the scholarship with the available budget. The manual calculation is only an example. For all data, it is using the software Matlab R2015b calculation tool. Steps to use Matlab are provided below.

1. Open the software and then type "fuzzy" in the Command Window to bring up a new window.
2. By default, Matlab provides FIS Mamdani with one input variable and one output variable. Suppose you want to add an input variable, so you must click "Edit – Add variable – Input". Next, change the variable name and range.
3. Create membership functions for each variable by clicking "Edit – Membership Functions". Choose a variable, rename the set then choose a type.
4. Add rules by clicking "Edit – Rules" then enter the rules.
5. View the results by clicking "View – Rules". Enter the value of each variable in "input" then press "enter".

4. Results and Discussion

Data from all scholarship recipients consists of institution and tuition fees. Fuzzy logic uses numeric data for input. Therefore, data was converted into the distance [7] and minimum regency wage [4] based on the studied assumptions to determine the scholarship amount.

4.1 Variables Definition

The information of the units and their respective ranges are obtained from data. The distance (**dist**) in kilometers is from 0 to 1062. Minimum regency wage (**wage**) and tuition fee (**tuft**) in millions of IDR range from 1.7 to 3.87 and 0.4 to 5, respectively. Fuzzy variables are defined from the information before. There are four kinds of such variables consisting of three input variables and one output variable. The input variables are **dist**, **wage**, and **tuft**, while the output variable is the scholarship amount (**schl**). From each variable will be formed three fuzzy sets.

4.2 Membership Functions Formulation

The universe talks of each variable obtained from the maximum and minimum values. The **dist** variable conversation universe is [0 1062], meaning that the allowed operating values are between 0 to 1062. It is the same for **wage** [1.7 3.87], **tuft** [0.4 5], and **schl** [4 10]. The membership function converts subjective values into objective values [6]. Membership functions can be defined on each fuzzy set based on linear and triangular curve representations.

The fuzzy sets of **dist** variable are NEAR, MEDIUM, and FAR.

Graph 1. Membership Function of Distance

The fuzzy sets of **wage** variable are LOW, MIDDLE, AND HIGH.

Graph 2. Membership Function of Regency Minimum Wage

The fuzzy sets of **tuft** variable are LOW, MIDDLE, AND HIGH.

Graph 3. Membership Function of Tuition Fee

The fuzzy sets of **schl** variable are LOW, MIDDLE, AND HIGH.

Graph 4. Membership Function of Scholarship Amount

4.3 Rules Determination

Fuzzy logic works based on the rules formed by IF-THEN. This rule expresses the input-output relationship. There are 81 rules from all possibilities of four variables with three fuzzy sets in each. Based on the results of consultations with the staff of the Sub-Division of Finance who manages the scholarships [3], there are 27 rules left. The rules used are according to human instinct reasoning. The thing to note is the number of certain fuzzy sets of the three input variables. For example, if a case with **dist** NEAR, **wage** LOW, and **tuit** HIGH, it follows from the provision that **schl** is MIDDLE.

4.4 Calculation

The calculation by Mamdani method manually is showed for one case as follows. Next, all the data was using the software. Let **dist** = 92, **wage** = 2.34, and **tuit** = 0.5 are the information from a candidate.

There are four steps of calculation. First, fuzzification by substitute the value obtained for each variable for the membership function of each fuzzy set. It will get the degree of membership, i.e.:

$$\begin{aligned}\mu_{dist_{NEAR}} &= 0.8267; \mu_{dist_{MEDIUM}} = 0.1733; \mu_{dist_{FAR}} = 0; \\ \mu_{wage_{LOW}} &= 0.4101; \mu_{wage_{MIDDLE}} = 0.5899; \mu_{wage_{HIGH}} = 0; \\ \mu_{tuit_{LOW}} &= 0.9565; \mu_{tuit_{MIDDLE}} = 0.0435; \mu_{tuit_{HIGH}} = 0;\end{aligned}$$

Second, inference by apply implication function Min to obtain α_i value, for some i^{th} rule. Third, the composition uses the Max method for all the rules from the results in the previous step. We have

$$\max_{LOW} = 0.5899, \max_{MIDDLE} = 0.1733, \text{ and } \max_{HIGH} = 0.$$

The modification of the fuzzy region and applying it to the output using the OR (union) operator.

Graph 5. Area of Composition Result

There are four areas A1, A2, A3, and A4. So $a_1, a_2, a_3,$ and a_4 values will be searched by substitute to **schl** MIDDLE set. We have $a_1 = 5.2303, a_2 = 6.4801, a_3 = 9.4801$. Therefore, we have the membership function for the composition result.

Last, defuzzification with Centroid method by calculate the moment of each area. We have

$$M1 = 3.3495, M2 = 2.7383, M3 = 4.1489, M4 = 0.4349$$

and

$$A1 = 0.7258, A2 = 0.4769, A3 = 0.5199, A4 = 0.045.$$

The z-weighted average is 6.0373 obtained by dividing the total of moment with the total of area. Finally, the amount of scholarship for this case is 6,037,300 IDR.

Continue counting for all data, the scholarship amount varies from 5.79 to 7.42 million of IDR. The results of manual calculations are not much different than using the software. The decimal difference is the result of rounding off when calculating fractions. However, sometimes the total amount is over budget. So that the calculation is carried out proportionally with the formula:

$$\text{Scholarship Amount} = \frac{\text{schl}}{\text{total schl}} \cdot \text{Budget}$$

5. Conclusion and Suggestion

The determination of the scholarship amount can use FIS Mamdani in four steps. The first step is to define the variables. The **dist** variable is defined: [0 1062], meaning that the values allowed operated

are between 0 to 1062. Then the same applies to **wage**: [1.7 3.87], **tuit**: [0.4 5], and **schl**: [4 10]. Each variable has three fuzzy sets. The second step is to form membership functions from 12 fuzzy sets based on linear and triangular curve representations. The third step is to determine the 27 rules used from the initial 81 rules. The rules are chosen based on ten agreed terms. The fourth step is to calculate input using the Mamdani method. The methods are to substitute **dist**, **wage**, and **tuit** data to the membership function; find the minimum value for each of the 27 rules; find the maximum value in each fuzzy set of the **schl**, and; find the area center point in the composition.

The manual calculation results have only decimal differences compared to the use of software caused by the rounding process. So based on the results of the study, FIS Mamdani can be recommended to determine the scholarship amount decision because the results are close to the available budget. The final results varied from 5,781,194 IDR to 7,408,715 IDR under the total of 649,999,916 IDR based on the data of 100 scholarship recipients.

The institution can use the results of this study as a new alternative in determining the amount of the scholarship. It clarifies the scholarship amount received by each prospective scholarship recipient. Another advantage is that clearly defined rules and boundaries are considered capable of reducing human subjectivity. The same method is also able to be applied to other similar problems.

Further researchers might determine the amount of scholarship by adding other related variables. The fuzzy inference system used is not only the Mamdani method. More suitable and effective ways can be identified later by comparing to others.

References

- [1] A.N. Rochim, Implementasi Algoritma Fuzzy Logic pada Penilaian Kelayakan Sistem Perkreditan Motor PT Federal International Finance dengan Menggunakan Metode Mamdani. (FIK UDINUS, Skripsi, 2017)
- [2] D. Lestari, Permasalahan Pelik Beasiswa Nasional (4 September 2019).
- [3] Endang, (private communication).
- [4] F. Zahir, UMP, UMK, dan UMR Setiap Daerah di Tahun 2019 (11 Oktober 2019)
- [5] Google Inc. *Google Maps* (11 October 2019).
- [6] Iksal, Saefudin, & A. Ilham, Rancang Bangun Sistem Pengendali Suhu Ruang Menggunakan *Fuzzy Logic*, *Jurnal Penelitian dan Pengabdian Masyarakat* 4(2) (2016) pp. 2017-212.
- [7] K. Nisa', *Info Beasiswa Banyuwangi Cerdas* (5 September 2019).
- [8] K.H. Lee, *First Course on Fuzzy Theory and Applications*. (Springer, Berlin, 2005).
- [9] L.A. Ayuningtyas, M. Irfan, & Jumadi, Analisa Perbandingan Logik Fuzzy Metode Tsukamoto, Sugeno, dan Mamdani (Studi Kasus: Prediksi Jumlah Pendaftar Mahasiswa Baru Fakultas Sains Dan Teknologi Universitas Islam Negeri Sunan Gunung Djati Bandung), *Jurnal Teknik Informatika* 10(1) (2017).
- [10] L.A. Zadeh, Fuzzy sets as a basis for a theory of possibility, *Fuzzy sets and systems* 100(1) (1999), pp. 13-28.
- [11] Portal Informasi Indonesia, Indeks Pembangunan Manusia terus Meningkat (31 Agustus 2019).
- [12] S. Batubara, Analisis Perbandingan Metode Fuzzy Mamdani dan Fuzzy Sugeno untuk Penentuan Kualitas Cor Beton Instan, *IT Journal Research and Development* 2(1) (2017), pp. 1-11.
- [13] S. Kusumadewi, Analisis Desain Sistem Fuzzy menggunakan Tool Box Matlab. (Graha Ilmu, Yogyakarta, 2002).
- [14] S. Kusumadewi, *Artificial Intelligence (Teknik dan Aplikasinya) 1*. (Graha Ilmu, Yogyakarta, 2003).
- [15] Samingun, Indeks Pembangunan Manusia Kabupaten Barru 2015. (Diva Utama, Makassar, 2016).

ADIWIDYA 9

KAMIL PASCASARJANA ITB

Follow kanal informasi Adiwidya 9:

Instagram : **@adiwidya**itb****

Website : <http://kamilpasca.itb.ac.id/adiwidya-9/>

Prosiding Seminar Nasional
Adiwidya 9
Pascasarjana ITB

Alamat Redaksi

Keluarga Mahasiswa Islam (KAMIL) Pascasarjana ITB,
Gedung Kayu Lt. 2, Kompleks Masjid Salman ITB,
Jl. Ganesha No. 10, Bandung,
40132 <https://kamilpasca.itb.ac.id/>

9 772746 488075